

A Descriptive Study on the Knowledge Regarding Breast-Feeding Problems and its Management Among Post Natal Mothers in Selected Hospital, Dehradun, Uttarakhand

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ABSTRACT

A cross sectional design was used to assess the knowledge regarding breast-feeding problems and its management among 100 postnatal mothers who were selected by using purposive sampling technique. Data was collected by Structured Interview schedule and breast feeding assessment checklist. The findings of the study revealed that the overall mean knowledge score was 15 ± 3.33 . According to area the highest mean score was in the area of introduction about breast-feeding (7.14 ± 1.94) and lowest in engorgement of breast (1.22 ± 1.01). Rank wise assessment of breast-feeding problems shows that less than half 46% of the mothers were having painful nipple and only 14% and 13% of mothers were having inverted and cracked nipple. Majority 60% of postnatal mothers had average knowledge regarding breast-feeding problems and its management. From the study findings it could be concluded that postnatal mothers had average knowledge regarding breast-feeding problems and its management. Thus, health education programs are required to enhance the knowledge regarding postnatal breast problems.

Keyword: Breast-feeding problems and its management, postnatal mothers, Knowledge

INTRODUCTION

Mother's sacrifice in creating a healthy population we can't explain. After delivery during post natal period there is various breast related problems in the mother and mother having less knowledge related to these problems. It affects mother's health and baby's growth and development.¹

Breastfeeding is the important aspect to mothers and their babies at least six month. After delivery in the

post natal period mothers having several breast related issues like; painful nipple, cracked nipple, inverted or retracted nipple, which are important to treat, but mother don't give attention into their breast so it can lead serious health issues.²

Breastfeeding is natural but mother don't know about the breast feeding properly. so, educate mother about the breast-feeding and its complication to the mothers for future health. Proper education, encouragement provide knowledge and helpful for mother and their child.³

Breastfeeding is a normal after delivery. Some mothers stop breastfeeding after sometime of delivery and reasons is early weaning and painful breasts and painful nipples. After delivery engorgement of breast and breast swelling are two main causes which can leads to painful breasts and nipple injury. Engorgement is painful breasts due to excess milk and increased blood supply.⁴

Breast feeding is important 6 months for babies and mothers. After delivery there are various problems which affect mothers and baby's health so there is great need of giving attention and provide solution and treatment related to the breast feeding. Feeding is the way which helpful for the growth and development of the infant and prevent mothers from the breast related problems.⁵

Breastfeeding is the way to provide growth and development and provide proper care to babies it helps baby from the disease and also provide full nutrition. There are many solution and way to provide proper care to the mother. Provide education and

support to mother and educate family also that prevent breast related problems.⁶

METHODOLOGY

A cross sectional design was used to assess the knowledge regarding breast-feeding problems and its management among 100 postnatal mothers who were selected by using purposive sampling technique. Data was collected by Structured Interview and breast feeding assessment Checklist.

Section-A: Socio-demographic profile: Age, Educational status, Occupation, Type of family, Parity, Types of delivery, postnatal day, Area of living, previous knowledge about breast-feeding problems and its management

Section-B: Structured knowledge questionnaire: A structured knowledge questionnaire (31 questions) was developed to assess the knowledge of mothers regarding breast feeding problems and their management.

Section C: Breast-feeding problems assessment checklist: A breast-feeding problems assessment check-list was developed to assess the breast problems among postnatal mothers. There were total 10 statement included mothers related breast problems and newborn related problems in the check-list.

RESULT

The analysis and interpretation of the observation are given in the following section.

Table no.1 Frequency and percentage distribution of selected personal profile of study participants

n=100

S. no.	Demographic variables	Frequency (%)	Percentage (%)
1.	Age in years		
	a) 19-24	33	33
	b) 25-30	50	50
	c) 31-36	17	17
2.	Educational status		
	a) No formal education	06	06
	b) Primary education	06	06
	c) Secondary education	14	14
	d) Higher secondary	19	19
e) Graduation & above	55	55	
3.	Occupational status	79	79
	a) Unemployed	21	21
4.	Type of family		
	a) Nuclear	15	15
	b) Joint	85	85
5.	Parity		
	a) Primipara	52	52
	b) Multipara	43	43
	c) Grand multipara	05	05
6.	Type of delivery		
	a) Normal vaginal delivery	37	37
	b) LSCS	63	63
7.	Postnatal Day		
	a) 1	07	07
	b) 2	38	38
	c) 3	38	38
	d) 4-7	17	17
8.	Area of living		
	a) Urban	21	21
	b) Rural	79	79

9.(a)	Previous knowledge regarding breast-feeding problems and its management		
	a) Yes	13	13
	b) No	87	87
(b)	Source of information (n=13)		
	Internet	13	13

Table No.2: Knowledge score regarding breast feeding problems among postnatal mothers.

n=100

Knowledge score	Total score	Range of score	Median	Mean \pm SD	Mean %
	31	7-23	15	15 \pm 3.33	48.38

Table no. 2. Shows description of knowledge scores regarding breast feeding problems and its managements. Total score was 31. The lowest range of score was 7 and the highest range of score was 23. The mean score was 15 \pm 3.33. Mean percentage for knowledge score was 48.38 %.

Table 3: Area wise level of knowledge regarding breast-feeding problems and its management among postnatal mothers

n=100

S. no	Area wise level of knowledge	Total Item	Mean \pm SD	Mean %
1	Introduction regarding breast-feeding	11	7.14 \pm 1.94	64.90
2	Breast engorgement	4	1.22 \pm 1.01	30.5
3	Mastitis and cracked nipples	4	1.39 \pm 0.98	34.75
4	Inverted nipple	3	1.4 \pm 0.84	46.66
5	Breast abscess	3	1.26 \pm 0.70	42
6	Oral thrush	4	1.75 \pm 1.12	58.33
7	Poor sucking reflex	2	0.77 \pm 0.60	38.5

Table no. 3 shows that the level of knowledge according to area the highest mean score was in the area of introduction about breast-feeding (7.14 \pm 1.94) and lowest in engorgement of breast (1.22 \pm 1.01). Hence it was interpreted that all seven domain level of knowledge was not satisfactory.

Table 4: Identify and rank of the breast feeding problems among the postnatal mothers

n=100

Breast feeding problems	Frequency & percentage (%)	Rank
Pain full nipple	46	1
Engorgement of breast	40	2
Inflammation of breast	28	3
Poor sucking reflex	25	4
Oral thrush in baby	25	5
Inverted nipple	14	6
Cracked nipple	13	7

Table 4: Shows that the rank wise description of breast feeding problems. These problems were divided into 8 ranks. (46%) was comes under Rank 1 painful nipple, Rank 2 engorgement of breast (40%), Rank 3 inflammation of breast (28%), In view of poor sucking reflex and oral thrush (25 %) was comes under Rank 4, 5, In case of inverted nipple (14%) was comes under Rank 6 and (13%) having cracked nipples in Rank 7.

Figure 1: Percentage wise distribution of Level of knowledge of postnatal mothers regarding Breast Feeding problems and its management

Figure no.1: illustrate those majority (60%) postnatal mothers had Average knowledge, (39%) of them had good knowledge and only (1%) was in very good knowledge on breast feeding problems and its management.

TableNo.5: Association between levels of knowledge of postnatal mothers with their selected demographic variables.

n=100

S. No.	Demographic Variables	Below median	At \$ above median	χ^2	P value
1.	Age in years			1.82	0.40
	a) 19-24	16	17		
	b) 25-30	23	27		
	c) 30-36	05	12		
2.	Educational Status			#0.41	0.28
	a) No formal education	04	02		
	b) Educated	43	51		
3.	Occupational Status			1.09	0.29
	a) Unemployed	35	44		
	b) Employed	12	09		
4.	Type of family			0.03	0.84
	a) Nuclear	07	08		
	b) Joint	42	43		
5.	Parity			0.31	0.57
	a) Primiparous	22	30		
	b) Multiparous	23	25		
6.	Type of delivery			0.12	0.71
	a) Normal vaginal delivery	19	18		
	b) LSCS	30	33		
7.	Postnatal Day			0.39	0.26
	a) 1-3	37	46		
	b) 4-7	09	08		
8.	Area of living			0.004	0.94
	a) Rural	37	42		
	b) Urban	10	11		
9.	Previous knowledge regarding breast-feeding problems and its management			0.0001	0.99
	a) Yes	06	07		
	b) No	40	47		

* Significant at $df_1=3.841$, $df_2=6.97$ at $p < 0.05$

fisher exact

The data presented in **Table no.5** shows that the description of association of knowledge with their selected demographic variables. The result indicates that there was no significant association found between knowledge score with their selected demographic variables such as Age, Educational status, Occupation, Type of family, Parity, Types of delivery, Postnatal day, Area of living, previous knowledge about breast-feeding problems and its management.

Hence it is interpreted that demographic variables did not have any influence on knowledge score of postnatal mothers.

DISCUSSION

The purpose of the study is to assess the knowledge regarding breast-feeding problems and its management among postnatal mothers in Himalayan hospital, Dehradun, Uttarakhand.

A cross sectional design was used to assess the knowledge regarding breast-feeding problems and its management among 100 postnatal mothers who were selected by using purposive sampling technique. Data was collected by Structured Interview and breast feeding assessment Checklist.

The result revealed that the mean score was 15 ± 3.33 . Mean percentage for knowledge score was 48.38%. The result indicates that there was no significant association found between knowledge score with their selected demographic variables such as Age, Educational status, Occupation, Type of family, Parity, Types of delivery, Postnatal day, Area of living, previous knowledge about breast-feeding problems and its management. The result was supported by the finding of the study conducted by Pushkar A T, Patel V P and Patel B R (2016) to assess Knowledge regarding selected postnatal breast problems and their management among postnatal mothers.

CONCLUSION

The findings of the study concluded that only 60% postnatal mothers had average knowledge regarding breast feeding problems and its management which indicated that there was still lack of knowledge in few aspects of breast-feeding problems. Thus, health education programs are required to enhance the knowledge among postnatal mothers as well as

antenatal mothers which may further help to reduce breast problems in postnatal period.

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